

Medium and short-term prognosis of load demand for the Greek Island of Tilos using artificial neural networks and human thermal comfort-discomfort biometeorological data

Moustris K.^{1,*}, Kavadias K.A.², Zafirakis D.², Kaldellis J.K.², Zafeiraki E.²

¹ Laboratory of Fluid Mechanics, Mechanical Engineering Department, University of West Attica, 250 Thivon and P. Ralli Str., GR-12244 Athens, Greece

² Soft Energy Applications & Environmental Protection Lab, Mechanical Engineering Department, University of West Attica, 250 Thivon and P. Ralli Str., GR-12244 Athens, Greece

*corresponding author e-mail: kmoustris@puas.gr

Abstract The objective of the present work is the medium and short term forecasting of load demand (LD) in Tilos Island, Greece. For this purpose, Artificial Neural Network (ANN) models were developed to predict the LD in Tilos Island 24 hours ahead in hourly intervals (medium-term prognosis) and 24 hours ahead in 10 minutes intervals (short-term prognosis). For training the ANNs, meteorological data covering the 2015-2017 period, were used. These data have been recorded in 1 minute intervals by a meteorological mast which has been installed in a specific location in Tilos Island. Furthermore, a biometeorological human thermal comfort-discomfort index was calculated and used also during the training procedure. For the validation of the developed ANN forecasting models well established statistical evaluation indices were applied. Results show that in all cases, for both medium and short-term LD prognoses, the developed ANN forecasting models present a remarkable ability to predict LD with high accuracy. The proposed load demand forecasting models enable the design of an energy demand information tool for end-users and transmission system operators.

1 Introduction

Global environmental concerns, decreasing fossil fuel reserves, and government policies are expected to increase the share of renewables in global electricity generation from 19% in 2008 to almost a third in 2035 (Vandael et al. 2012). During the last decade, increased interest is recorded in the field of smart grids (Malik and Lehtonen 2016, Tuballa and Abundo 2016). Smart grid is a promising power delivery infrastructure integrated with communication and information technologies. Its bi-directional communication and electricity flow enable both utilities and customers to monitor, predict, and manage energy usage (Liu et al. 2012). Smart Grid is designed to integrate advanced communication-networking technologies into electrical power grids to make them smarter (Gao et al. 2012). Lund et al. illustrate why electricity smart grids should be seen as part of an overall smart energy system (Lund et al. 2012). The smart grid is conceived of as an electric grid that can deliver electricity in a controlled, smart way from points of generation to active consumers (Siano 2014).

Furthermore, the development of novel demand side management (DSM) techniques (Haider et al. 2016, Stathopoulos et al. 2014) that can facilitate the latter operation is a very important issue. DSM is one of the most important functions in a smart grid that allows customers to make informed decisions regarding their energy consumption and helps the energy providers to reduce the peak load demand and reshape the load profile (Logenthiran et al. 2012). Most of the existing DSM programs focus primarily on the interactions between a utility company and its customers/users (Mohsenian-Rad et al. 2010). According to Ramchurn et al., central to the

vision of the smart grid is the deployment of smart meters that will allow autonomous software agents, representing the consumers, to optimize their use of devices and heating in the smart home while interacting with the grid (Ramchurn et al. 2011). However, without some form of coordination, the population of agents may end up with overly-homogeneous optimized consumption patterns that may generate significant peaks in demand in the grid. These peaks, in turn, reduce the efficiency of the overall system, increase carbon emissions, and may even, in the worst case, cause blackouts.

For the operation of autonomous micro-grids, an important task is to share the load demand using multiple distributed generation units (He and Li 2012) as well as the use of a good and sufficient load demand forecasting tool (Matallanas et al. 2012). For this purpose, a lot of papers demonstrate the development and the use of a load demand forecasting tool for the best management of micro-grids. Hahn et al. gave an overview over the various models and methods used to predict future load demands (Hahn et al. 2009). Raza and Khosravi wrote an overview of load demand forecasting techniques based on artificial intelligence for smart grids and buildings (Raza and Khosravi 2015). According to their overview, the published literature show the potential of the ANN techniques for effective load forecasting in order to achieve the concept of smart grids and buildings. Moghram and Rahman presented a comparative evaluation of five short-term load forecasting techniques such as Multiple Linear Regression, Stochastic Time Series, General Exponential Smoothing, State Space Method and Knowledge-Based Approach (Moghram and Rahman 1989). Park et al presented an ANN approach for electric load forecasting (Park et al. 1991). The developed ANN was used to learn the relationship among past, current and future temperatures and loads. In order to provide the forecasted load, the ANN interpolates among the load and temperature data in a training data set. Senjyu et al. proposed a one-hour-ahead load forecasting ANN model using the correction of similar day data (Senjyu et al. 2002). In the proposed prediction method, the forecasted load power is obtained by adding a correction to the selected similar day data.

The main objective of the present work is the development of two different ANN forecasting models in order to predict the LD in Tilos Island, Greece, for two different forecasting horizons. The first ANN model was trained to forecast the LD 24 hours ahead in hourly intervals (medium-term prognosis). The second ANN model was trained to forecast the LD 2 hours ahead in 10 minutes intervals (short-term prognosis).

2 Data and Methodology

The specific work was made in the frame of TILOS project. TILOS is a European research project engaging 13 participating enterprises and institutes from 7 European countries (DE, FR, EL, UK, SE, IT, ES). The project's main goal is to demonstrate the potential of local/small-scale battery storage to serve a multipurpose role within an island micro-grid that also interacts with a main electricity network. Among others, the project aims to achieve large-scale Renewable Energy Sources (RES) penetration and asset value maximization through the optimum integration of a hybrid RES (wind and PV) power station together with advanced battery storage, smart metering and DSM. The project's objectives will be accomplished through the development and operation of an integrated, smart micro-grid on the Island of Tilos. Tilos Island belongs to the island complex of Dodecanese on the south-eastern part of the Aegean Sea, and is interconnected to the host grid of Kos and Kalymnos islands via an undersea cable. For training the ANNs, meteorological and LD data were collected covering the period 2015-2017 (almost 3 years). More specifically, air temperature, relative humidity, wind speed,

barometric pressure and solar irradiation data have been recorded through a system of two separate meteorological masts that have been installed to the PV farm location, in the center of Tilos Island, and next to the wind turbine on the North side of the island. Furthermore, LD data have been recorded by a number of dedicated grid load meters measuring the island's load demand. All the aforementioned data have been recorded by one minute step measurements.

ANNs are a branch of artificial intelligence developed in the 1950s aiming at imitating the biological brain architecture. They are parallel-distributed systems made of many interconnected nonlinear processing elements (PEs), called neurons (McCulloch and Pitts 1943, Hect-Nielsen 1990). A renewal of interest has grown exponentially in the last decades, mainly for the availability of suitable hardware that has made them convenient for fast data analysis and information processing.

In this work, the Multilayer Perceptron (MLP) ANN models were developed to forecast the LD of the entire Tilos island region. MLP is the most commonly used type of ANN topology. Its structure consists of processing elements (PEs) and connections. The PEs, called neurons, are arranged in layers: the input layer, one or more hidden layers, and the output layer (Hect-Nielsen 1990, Moustris et al. 2010a).

The best architecture of the developed models was selected after a trial and error method. Both of the two developed ANN models have one input layer, one hidden layer and one output layer (1-1-1) with sigmoid hidden neurons and linear output neurons. The network was trained with Levenberg-Marquardt backpropagation algorithm (Nastos et al. 2011). TahnAxon was preferred as the activation function of the model by the virtue of being successful in interrelating the input and output parameters.

Initially, using the one-minute values of wind speed and air temperature the corresponding values of a biometeorological index known as Cooling Power (CP) were calculated (Moustris et al. 2010b, Nastos et al. 2011). CP index describes the human thermal comfort-discomfort due to high air temperature (heat waves). From the point of authors' view, the use of CP values is very important during the ANNs training. This is due to the fact that the population of Tilos Island is changing during the hot period of the year. At the summer period the population of the island is a multiple of the normal population due to tourists. Hence, the LD is increasing rapidly because of the extended use of air conditioning systems due to high temperatures and uncomfortable human thermal sensation. By using CP, the developed ANNs can be trained and "understand" that the increasing of LD is due to the uncomfortable human thermal conditions and the use of air conditioning systems.

For each forecasting horizon (medium and short-term) the data set was separated in to three different subsets (Moustris et al. 2010a). The first subset includes the 80% of the data and was used for the training phase, the second 10% of the data which was used for the cross validation test and the remaining 10% was used for the testing phase.

For the evaluation of the two developed ANN models forecasting ability, appropriate statistical evaluation indices were applied (Moustris et al. 2010a, Nastos et al. 2011). More precisely, the mean bias error (MBE), the root mean square error (RMSE), the mean absolute percentage error (MAPE), the index of agreement (IA) and the coefficient of determination (R^2).

3 Results

The first of the two developed ANN models was trained to predict the LD in Tilos Island 24 hours ahead in hourly intervals (medium term prognosis). It takes into account parameters of the three (3) previous days and forecasts the 24 hourly values of LD for the next day. For example,

to obtain prediction on Wednesday, the model uses as input parameters data of the 3 previous days (Sunday, Monday and Tuesday) and forecasts the 24 hourly values of ED for the next day (Thursday). The model is able to forecast the 24 LD hourly values of the next day at any time of the day (from 01:00 up to 24:00). The input and output-target data for the training of the above ANN model are presented in the Table 1.

Table 1. Input and output-target data for the appropriate training of medium term forecasting ANN model.

Input Data	Output Data-Target
The number (M) of the month (from 1 up to 12) of the three previous days The number (D) of the day (from 1 up to 31) of the three previous days The hour (H) of the day (from 1 up to 24) of the three previous days The day type (DT)-(Monday=1 up to Sunday=7) of the three previous days The total global solar irradiation (W/m^2) on the horizontal plane at the (H) hour from the three previous days The minimum, maximum and average relative humidity (%) of the (H) hour from the three previous days The minimum, maximum and average value of Cooling Power index of the (H) hour from the three previous days The total load demand (W) of the (H) hour from the three previous days The number (M) of the month (from 1 up to 12) of the next day The number (D) of the day (from 1 up to 31) of the next day The hour (H) of the day (from 1 up to 24) of the next day The day type (DT)-(Monday=1 up to Sunday=7) of the next day	The load demand (Watt) of the (H) hour of the next day

Figure 1 depicts the error histogram (forecasted-observed hourly values of LD) according to the developed medium term forecasting model (Figure 1a) as well as the scatter plot between the observed vs the forecasted hourly values of LD (Figure 1b).

(a)

(b)

Fig. 1. Error histogram (a) and scatter plot between the observed and the forecasted hourly LD values (b). Medium term-prognosis.

The second model was trained to forecast the LD for the whole Island of Tilos in 10-minute intervals for the next 24 consecutive hours. For example, on 10:00 o'clock in the morning the developed model forecasts the LD for 10:10, 10:20, 10:30, 10:40, 10:50, 11:00, 11:10, ..., up to 10:00 o'clock in the morning of the next day. The same forecast is executed every 10 minutes for the next 24 hours (24hours x 6 intervals per hour=144 forecasted values). The input and output-target data for the training of the above ANN model are shown in Table 2.

Table 2. Input and output-target data for the appropriate training of short term forecasting ANN model.

Input Data	Output Data-Target
The number of the month of the previous day (1 for January up to 12 for December) The number of the day of the previous day (1 up to 30 or 31) The hour of the prediction of the previous day (0 up to 23) The minute (10mintues interval) of the prediction of the previous day (10 up to 60) Total solar irradiation (W/m^2) on the horizontal plane of the same 10minutes interval of the previous day Minimum average relative humidity (%)of the same 10minutes interval of the previous day Maximum average relative humidity (%)of the same 10minutes interval of the previous day Average relative humidity (%)of the same 10minutes interval of the previous day Absolute minimum value of Cooling Power index of the same 10minutes interval of the previous day Absolute maximum value of Cooling Power index of the same 10minutes interval of the previous day Average value of Cooling Power index of the same 10minutes interval of the previous day Total energy demand (W) of the same 10minutes interval of the previous day The number of the month of the forecasted day (1 for January up to 12 for December) The number of the day of the forecasted day (1 up to 30 or 31) The hour of the prediction of the forecasted day (0 up to 23) The minute (10mintues interval) of the prediction of the forecasted day (10 up to 60)	The load demand (Watt) of the same 10min interval for the next day

Figure 2 depicts the error histogram (forecasted-observed 10min values of LD) according to the developed short-term forecasting model (Figure 2a), as well as the scatter plot between the observed and the forecasted 10min values of LD (Figure 2b).

Fig. 2. Error histogram (a) and scatter plot between the observed and the forecasted 10min LD values (b). Short-term prognosis.

Table 4 presents the results of the statistical indices for evaluating the forecasting ability of the developed ANN models.

Table 4. Statistical evaluation indices.

Model	MBE (kW)	RMSE (kW)	MAPE (%)	IA	R ²
Medium term prognosis (hourly)	-4.7	37.3	7.8	0.983	0.934
Short term prognosis (10min)	-1.5	32.6	7.2	0.987	0.949

According to Table 4, as well as to Figure 1, it seems that the first developed ANN forecasting model presents a remarkable forecasting ability to predict the LD for the next 24hours (hourly forecasting step, medium-term prognosis). More specifically, the developed model underestimates the LD by 4.7kW. Also, the RMSE is equal to 37.3kW with a mean hourly value of LD for the whole island of Tilos around to 346kW. The above conclusions are also confirmed by the MAPE value which is equal to 7.8%. The IA is equal to 0.983 meaning that the forecasted LD values are very close to the corresponding observed values and finally, R² is equal to 0.934 indicating a strong linear correlation between the forecasted LD values and the corresponding observed values (Figure 1b). Finally, the error distribution (forecasted-observed hourly values) depicts that 86.9% of the differences lay between ± 50 kW (Figure 1a).

The same conclusions arise also for the second ANN developed model which forecasts the LD for 10min intervals for the next 24hours (short-term prognosis). Concretely, the MBE is -1.5 kW which means that in an average level the developed model underestimates the LD by 1.5kW. Also, the RMSE is equal to 32.6kW with a mean 10min value of LD for the whole island of Tilos around to 346kW. The value of MAPE (7.2%) confirms the above conclusions. The IA is equal to 0.987 indicating that the forecasted LD values are very close to the corresponding observed values and finally, R² is equal to 0.949 which means that there is a strong linear correlation between the forecasted LD values and the corresponding observed values (Figure 2b). According to the error distribution (forecasted-observed 10min values) 90.9% of the differences are lying between ± 50 kW (Figure 2a).

4 Conclusions

In the present work two different ANN models have been developed in order to forecast the LD in the Tilos Island, Greece. For this purpose, meteorological and load demand data have been used covering the time period 2015-2015.

Results showed that the developed models present a remarkable prognostic ability to forecast the LD in two different forecasting horizons, first in hourly bases for the next 24hours (medium-term prognosis) and second in 10min intervals for the next 24hours (short-term prognosis).

Authors believe that with the developed ANNs forecasting models the system administrator will be able to have a very good point of view concerning LD for the next 24 consecutive hours in a medium and short prognostic term-step. This is an optimistic result in order to design an automated micro-grid information tool that could much facilitate the tasks of the energy management system. I

n any case, further investigation is encouraged so as to increase the forecasting ability of the proposed load demand dynamic forecasting models using, in a parallel process as primary inputs, data from numerical weather prediction models.

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